

A THIRD-ORDER APPROACH FOR THE REINFORCEMENT OF CONCRETE SHELLS WITH EXTERNAL COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: It is presented a third-order approach for the reinforcement of concrete shells with external composite laminates. Reinforced concrete (RC) structures are a very important sector in civil construction industry. Corrosion of steel re-bars is a common problem, due to the porosity of concrete. The use of external composites (FRP) bonded to the faces of concrete are today a good solution to the strengthening and retrofitting of degraded structures [1-3]. The behaviour of such structures is highly non-linear. The need for non-linear geometrical and material models implies the use of numerical methods such as the finite element method [4-6]. The use of higher-order shear deformations is now common in the analysis of composite laminates [7-10]. In this paper it is proposed the use of a third-order shear-deformation theory in the analysis of concrete shells strengthened with external composite unidirectional strips. This theory is an alternative to the first-order theory proposed by Ferreira et al [11]. The theory is implemented in a shell element [11] that allows for a layered discretisation of the laminate materials. A perfect plastic and a strain-hardening plasticity approach are used to model the compressive behavior of the concrete. A dual criterion for yielding and crushing in terms of stresses and strains is considered, which is complemented by a tension cut-off representation. The material law for the unidirectional composites is linear elastic/brittle. A simply-supported concrete beam, reinforced with composite strips is analysed. The effects of the reinforcement, the use of the third-order theory and the comparison of composite strengthening and steel rebars on concrete are discussed.

KEYWORDS: concrete shells, finite element analysis, frp reinforcement, composite materials, composite reinforcement, third-order theory

INTRODUCTION

Reinforced concrete (RC) structures are very important in civil construction industry.

For many years the structural analysis of RC was based on empirical laws and elasticity equations. Concrete is a complex material with cracking, tension stiffening,

plasticity, and non-linear properties. Numerical methods such as the finite element method are needed for such an analysis [4-6].

Corrosion of steel re-bars is a common problem, due to the porosity of concrete. The use of external composites (FRP) bonded to the faces of concrete are today a good solution to the retrofiting of degraded structures [1-3]. The need for numerical methods is even greater than with conventional reinforced concrete.

In this paper it is intended to study the behavior of reinforced concrete, strengthened with thin unidirectional composite strips, mainly on the tension side, by the use of the finite element method.

The non-linear material model for the concrete and for the composite strips is implemented in a shell element. The geometrical and material non-linear behavior is accounted for [11-13]. Some results are discussed.

COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOR OF CONCRETE

The non-linear behavior of concrete is inelastic. A perfect plastic and a strain-hardening plasticity approach are used to model the compressive behavior of the concrete. A dual criterion for yielding and crushing in terms of stresses and strains is considered, which is complemented by a tension cut-off representation.

The yield condition

The yield condition for thick plates and shells accounting for transverse shear effects is formulated in terms of the first two stress invariants as

$$f(I_1, J_2) = [\beta(3J_2) + \alpha I_1]^{1/2} = \sigma_0 \quad (1)$$

where α and β are material parameters and σ_0 is the effective stress obtained from a uniaxial compression test. Relating this expression to Kupfer's results [14], the material parameters are

$$\alpha = 0.355 \sigma_0, \quad \beta = 1.355 \quad (2)$$

In the perfectly plastic model σ_0 is taken as the ultimate stress f'_c obtained from a uniaxial compressive test. An elastic response is assumed up to when the effective stress reaches f'_c , after which a perfectly plastic response follows until the crushing surface is reached. Figure 1 illustrates the one-dimensional representation of both the perfectly plastic and the strain-hardening model [11,12].

The crushing condition

The crushing condition is a strain-controlled phenomenon. The lack of experimental information allows for a direct conversion of (1) into strains. Thus,

$$[\beta(3J'_2) + \alpha I'_1]^{1/2} = \varepsilon_u^2 \quad (3)$$

where I'_1 and J'_2 are strain invariants and ε_u is an ultimate total strain extrapolated from uniaxial test results.

Crushing or compressive type of fracture is assumed to occur when the effective total strain, reaches the limit value which is usually taken as the maximum compressive strain in a uniaxial compression test. Once crushing has occurred the concrete is assumed to lose all its characteristics of stiffness at the point under consideration. Therefore the corresponding elasticity matrix D is taken as a null matrix and the vector of total stresses is reduced to zero.

Fig. 1 : One-dimensional representation of the concrete constitutive model

TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF CONCRETE

The relative weakness of concrete in tension and the resulting cracking is a fundamental factor affecting the nonlinear behavior of reinforced concrete plates and shells. It is assumed that when concrete is subjected to a tensile stress it behaves like an elastic-brittle material. Formation of cracks is a brittle process and the concrete strength in the tension-loading direction goes abruptly to zero after such cracks have formed (figure 2).

SMEARED CRACK MODEL

In our analysis we are not interested in the tensile strength of concrete, but in the influence of the cracked concrete zones on the structural behavior. A simplified averaging procedure for finite element representation is adopted, based on smeared cracked concrete, which assumes that cracks are distributed across a region of the finite element [11,12].

In this model cracked concrete is supposed to remain a continuum and the material properties are then modified to account for the damage induced in the material. After the first crack has occurred the concrete becomes orthotropic with the material axes oriented along the directions of cracking (figure 2).

The response of concrete under tensile stresses is assumed to be linear elastic until the fracture surface is reached. This tensile type of fracture or cracking is governed by a maximum tensile stress criterion (tension cut-off). Cracks are assumed to form in planes perpendicular to the direction of maximum tensile stress, as soon as this stress reaches the specified concrete tensile strength f'_t . A sudden and total release of the normal stress in the affected direction, or its gradual relaxation according to a tension-stiffening diagram is adopted after cracking has occurred. The elasticity modulus and the Poisson's ratio are reduced to zero in the direction perpendicular to the cracked plane, and a reduced shear modulus is employed [11,12]. Before cracking, concrete is assumed to be an isotropic material, with the following stress strain relationship

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} & \frac{\nu E}{1-\nu^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu E}{1-\nu^2} & \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha G & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha G \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

with x and y being the axes in the plane of the structure and E the elasticity modulus, ν the Poisson's ratio, G the shear modulus, $G=E/2(1+\nu)$ and α the shear correction factor, $\alpha=5/6$. Taking 1 and 2 as the two principal stress directions in the plane of the structure, the stress-strain relationship for concrete cracked in the 1-direction (crack plane normal to 1-direction) is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12}^c & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{13}^c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha G \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where G^c is the reduced shear modulus of cracked concrete [11,12]. When the tensile stress in the 2-direction reaches the value f^t , a second cracked plane perpendicular to the first one is assumed to form and the stress-strain relationship for concrete cracked in two directions becomes

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{G_{12}^c}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{13}^c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{23}^c \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The cracked concrete is anisotropic and these relations must be transformed to the reference axes, similarly as done with composite materials.

BEHAVIOUR OF STEEL REBARS IN TENSION AND COMPRESSION

The steel reinforcing bars used in reinforced concrete structures are usually round with protrusions (ribs or lugs). These protrusions are responsible for better bond characteristics between the reinforcing bars and the surrounding concrete. Steel bars have an elasto-plastic behavior, defined by its yield strength, with a typical elasticity modulus of 210 GPa. A yield plateau, whose extension depends on the class of steel, is followed by a strain-hardening behavior up to failure. In this model the reinforcing bars are modeled as steel layers of equivalent thickness. Each steel layer exhibits a uniaxial response, having strength and stiffness characteristics in the bar direction only. The elasto-plastic behavior is treated incrementally as a one-dimensional problem.

BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE STRIPS IN TENSION AND COMPRESSION

Composite strips made usually from carbon/epoxy materials are bonded together at the tension face of concrete, in order to improve the tension characteristics of concrete. These strips are typically made from unidirectional composites, with unidirectional properties. They are

considered as elastic-brittle materials, with no yield strength, only ultimate strength. When the stresses at these layers reach the specified ultimate tensile strength of the composite material, the material is assumed to lose all its stiffness and strength, as in a typical concrete layer. The material characteristics are orthotropic and are defined as in equation (10) to (12). Typical composites made from unidirectional epoxy/carbon materials have modulus of 180 GPa and ultimate stress of about 1500 MPa.

SHEAR DEFORMATION THEORIES

First order shear deformation theories

Yang, Norris and Stavsky [9] and Stavsky [10] have developed a theory of deformation based on the work of Mindlin [15] and Reissner [14] for isotropic plates. The displacement field is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= u_o(x, y) + z\theta_x(x, y) \\ v(x, y, z) &= v_o(x, y) + z\theta_y(x, y) \\ w(x, y, z) &= w_o(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where u , v and w are the x , y and z displacements. The u_o , v_o and w_o are the mid-plane displacements, and θ_x and θ_y the rotations of the normal. Stress-strains relations can be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^o \\ \varepsilon_y^o \\ \gamma_{xy}^o \end{bmatrix} + z \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \underline{\varepsilon}^o + z\underline{\kappa} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} w_{,x} + \theta_x \\ w_{,y} + \theta_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\varepsilon_x^o = u_{o,x}, \varepsilon_y^o = v_{o,y}, \gamma_{xy}^o = v_{o,x} + u_{o,y} \quad (10)$$

$$\kappa_x = \theta_{x,x}, \kappa_y = \theta_{y,y}, \kappa_{xy} = \theta_{x,y} + \theta_{y,x}$$

are the membrane deformations and plane curvatures.

Fig. 2 : Behaviour of concrete under traction and smeared crack model and the corresponding material axes for concrete cracked in one direction

In each layer k of the laminate the stress-strain relations are obtained as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} \\ c_{12} & c_{22} & c_{23} \\ c_{13} & c_{23} & c_{33} \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix}_k ; \begin{bmatrix} \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} c_{44} & c_{45} \\ c_{45} & c_{55} \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{bmatrix}_k \quad (11)$$

where c_{ij} are elastic coefficients and $\{1,2,3\}$ are the principal material directions for each layer. This theory is simple, but introduces a shear correction coefficient [11,13] that affects only the shear terms.

Higher order shear deformation theories

The higher order shear deformation theories avoid the use of the shear correction factors by a better representation of the ‘‘normal’’ warping. Various theories were proposed in the literature [7-10]. The model proposed in this paper has the following displacement field

$$u = \underline{u}^0 + z\underline{\theta} + z^3\underline{\theta}^* \quad (12)$$

where $\underline{\theta}^*$ represents the higher order rotations.

In these theories the transverse displacement is constant throughout the plate or shell thickness. This theory has the advantage that no shear-correction factors are needed.

In sandwich laminates these theories present some difficulties. The layer-wise theory proposed allows for a better deformation analysis in the laminate.

FINITE ELEMENT IMPLEMENTATION

The theories presented so far were implemented in the degenerated shell element [4-6,17]. Two main coordinate systems are used in the element [17]. The global Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) , in relation to which the nodal coordinates and displacements are defined, and the curvilinear coordinate system (ξ, η, ζ) , where the shape functions N_k are expressed. The mid-surface of the element is defined by the ξ and η coordinates. In the Ahmad shell element ζ is a linear coordinate in the thickness direction and is only approximately normal to the shell mid-surface. Ahmad degenerated a three-dimensional brick element to a curved shell element, which has nodes at the mid-surface [17]. This element defines, in addition to the coordinate systems above referred, two more sets as can be seen in figure 4. A nodal Cartesian coordinates system (v_{1k}, v_{2k}, v_{3k}) is associated with each nodal point of the element and has its origin at the mid-surface. The unit vector $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{3k}$, constructed from the nodal coordinates of the top, \mathbf{x}_k^{top} , and bottom, \mathbf{x}_k^{bot} , surfaces at node k , determines the ‘normal’ direction v_{3k} , which is not necessarily perpendicular to the reference surface. The unit vectors $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{1k}$ (direction v_{1k}) and $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{2k}$ (direction v_{2k}) define the nodal rotations, β_{2k} and β_{1k} respectively, of the referred ‘normal’. The local Cartesian coordinate system (x', y', z') is used to define local stresses and strains at the sampling points wherein they must be calculated. The vector direction \mathbf{z}' is taken to be orthogonal to the surface $\zeta = \text{constant}$, the direction \mathbf{x}' is defined similarly as the direction of $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{1k}$ and, finally, \mathbf{y}' is obtained by the cross product of \mathbf{z}' and \mathbf{x}' . This coordinate system varies along the thickness of the element and it is useful to define the direction cosine matrix $\underline{\theta}$, which relates the transformations between the local and global coordinate systems; this matrix is defined by

$$\underline{\theta} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{x}}' & \bar{\mathbf{y}}' & \bar{\mathbf{z}}' \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{x}}'$, $\bar{\mathbf{y}}'$ and $\bar{\mathbf{z}}'$ are unit vectors along the directions \mathbf{x}' , \mathbf{y}' and \mathbf{z}' respectively.

The coordinates \mathbf{x} of a point within the element are obtained as

$$\mathbf{x} = [x, y, z]^T = \sum_{k=1}^n N_k(\xi, \eta) \left[\mathbf{x}_k^{mid} + h_k \zeta / 2 \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{3k} \right] \quad (14)$$

The displacements for the first order shear deformation are obtained as

$$\underline{\mathbf{u}} = \sum_{k=1}^n \underline{N}_k \underline{\mathbf{u}}_k^{med} + \sum_{k=1}^n \underline{N}_k \zeta \frac{h_k}{2} [V_{1k}, -V_{2k}] \begin{Bmatrix} \beta_{1k} \\ \beta_{2k} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

whereas for the third order theory are obtained as

$$\underline{\mathbf{u}} = \sum_{k=1}^n \underline{N}_k \underline{\mathbf{u}}_k^{med} + \sum_{k=1}^n \underline{N}_k \zeta \frac{h_k}{2} [V_{1k}, -V_{2k}] \begin{Bmatrix} \beta_{1k} \\ \beta_{2k} \end{Bmatrix} + \sum_{k=1}^n \underline{N}_k \left(\zeta \frac{h_k}{2} \right)^3 [V_{1k}, -V_{2k}] \begin{Bmatrix} \beta_{1k}^* \\ \beta_{2k}^* \end{Bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

for the other layers. In (16) β_{1k}^* and β_{2k}^* represent the higher-order rotations. The parameter n is the number of nodes per element, h_k is the shell thickness at node k , i.e. the respective ‘normal’ length, \mathbf{u}_k^{mid} and \mathbf{x}_k^{mid} are, respectively, the displacements and the global coordinates at the mid-surface, and $N_k(\xi, \eta)$ are the element shape functions.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

A single span beam tested by Bresler and Scordelis [18] is selected for analysis. The beam is simply supported, subjected to a concentrated load at mid-span and presenting a shear span to effective depth ratio of about 7. The type of failure experimentally observed for the beam was a brittle failure due to a flexure-compression action. The beam failed by crushing of the concrete compression zone nears mid-span. This example is a good example to compare the model developed for compression concrete, namely the perfect plastic and the hardening plastic models. In the experiment the beams were first loaded to about 30 percent of ultimate load in two or three increments and then the load was removed. The load was reapplied in small increments until failure occurred. The experimental curves available were obtained from the deflections recorded during the final cycle of loading from zero to ultimate. In the analysis the load is applied incrementally in one cycle from zero to ultimate.

The load conditions and the span are illustrated in figure 3. The stirrups are not considered in the analysis. The material properties are presented in table 1. A brittle failure by crushing of the concrete before yielding of the steel is expected, therefore the post-yield diagram of the main reinforcement is not of great importance in this study.

Taking advantage of symmetry, only one half of the span is analyzed. Four finite elements are used refining the mesh near the center where larger nonlinear effects are expected (fig 2). Selective integration is employed to obtain better representation of the material behavior particularly near the applied load.

Ten concrete layers of equal thickness and three smeared steel layers are used to discretise the beam through the thickness. The smeared thickness of each layer is specified in figure 2.

Mid-span deflections versus total load are plotted in figure 4. The numerical solutions performed with the present model, either by using the perfect plastic (PP) or the hardening plastic (HP) approach for concrete in compression are compared with the experimental curve. Excellent agreement is shown between the experimental and the hardening plastic (HP) results. The slight discrepancy for lower load range is attributed to the previously mentioned unloading and reloading experimental cycle. The slightly higher collapse load (2.6 %) may be due to the coarse thickness considered for the concrete top layer. One of the main steel reinforcement layers (the bottom one) starts to yield at $P=470$ kN, therefore the assumed steel

post-yield diagram may have some influence on the ultimate load. The results performed with the perfectly plastic (PP) model show a stiffer response for higher loads and a greater (unconservative) collapse load.

The third-order shear deformation approach seems to be efficient in the analysis of such structures.

In figure 4 it is also presented a load-displacement curve for the RC beam with a external 1 mm thick CFRP laminate in the tension side (bottom face). The overall load-displacement behaviour is much stiffer than for a RC beam without any laminate reinforcement.

Fig. 3 : Simply supported RC beam – Geometry, mesh, layered structure

Fig. 4 : Simply supported RC beam – Comparison of experimental and numerical results

CONCLUSIONS

The material and geometrical nonlinearity for reinforced concrete strengthened with fiber reinforced plastics was performed. The material model for concrete was based on a dual approach for compressive and tensile behavior, with degradation of properties due to cracking and crushing. Steel reinforcements are considered as uni-dimensional elasto-plastic solids, while composite reinforcements are considered as elasto-brittle solids. A third-order approach for the reinforcement of concrete shells with external composite laminates was presented. A perfect plastic and a strain-hardening plasticity approach were used to model the compressive behavior of the concrete. A dual criterion for yielding and crushing in terms of stresses and strains was considered, with a tension cut-off representation. The material law for the unidirectional composites is linear elastic/brittle. The concrete allows for elasto-plastic-brittle behavior. A simply-supported concrete beam, reinforced with composite strips was analysed. The effects of the reinforcement, the use of the third-order theory and the comparison of composite strengthening and steel rebars on concrete were discussed. A good agreement between the experimental and numerical results for RC beams was found. When strengthened with CFRP sheets the behaviour of the beam is stiffer as expected. The cracking by tension action is delayed to higher loads. The overall behaviour is much stiffer. However, this model does not take into account the influence of the adhesive layer, which may change the load-displacement behaviour.

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REFERENCES

1. U. Meyer, A. Winistorfer, Retrofitting of structures through external bonding of CFRP sheets, Proc. 2nd Int. RILEM Symposium FRPRCS-2, E&FN Spon, London, 1995.
2. L. Juvandes, J.A. Figueiras, A.T. Marques, Performance of concrete beams strengthened with CFRP laminates, Fiber Composites in Infrastructure, H. Saadatmanesh and M.R. Eshani (Eds), Second International Conference on Composites in Infrastructure, Tucson, 1998.
3. A. Nanni, F. Focacci, C.A. Cobb, Proposed procedure for the design of RC flexural members strengthened with FRP sheets, Fiber Composites in Infrastructure, H. Saadatmanesh and M.R. Eshani (Eds), Second International Conference on Composites in Infrastructure, Tucson, 1998.
4. O. C. Zienkiewicz, The Finite Element Method, McGraw-Hill, 1991.
5. M.A. Crisfield, Non-linear finite element analysis of solids and structures, John Wiley & Sons, 1991.
6. K.J. Bathe, Finite element procedures in engineering analysis, Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, 1982.
7. J.N. Reddy, A simple higher-order theory for laminated composite plates, J.of Applied Mech., Vol.51, 1984, pp. 745-751.
8. T. Kant e D.R.J. Owen, A refined higher-order C^o plate bending element, Comp.Struct., Vol.15, 1982, pp. 177-183.
9. P.C. Yang, C.H. Norris, Y. Stavsky, Elastic wave propagation in heterogeneous plates, Int. J. Sol. Struct., Vol.2, 1966, pp. 665-684.
10. Y. Stavsky, Bending and stretching of laminated anisotropic elastic plates, J.Eng. Mech. Div., Vol.87, 1961, pp. 31-56.
11. A. J. M. Ferreira, Numerical models for the analysis of composite and sandwich laminated structures (in portuguese) Ph.D. Thesis, Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto, Porto, 1997.
12. D.R.J. Owen, J.A. Figueiras, Ultimate load analysis of reinforced concrete plates and shells, in Finite Element Software for Plates and Shells, E.Hinton e D.R.J.Owen (Eds.), Pineridge Press, 1984.
13. J. A. Figueiras, Ultimate load analysis of Anisotropic and Reinforced Concrete plates and shells, Ph. D. Thesis, c/ph/72/83, University College of Swansea, 1983.
14. H. Kupfler, K.H. Hilsdorf and H. Rush, Behaviour of concrete under biaxial stresses, Proceedings, American Concrete Institute, Vol.66, n° 8, 1969, pp. 656-666.
15. R.D. Mindlin - Influence Of Rotary Inertia And Shear On Flexural Motions Of Isotropic, Elastic Plates. J. Appl. Mech. 18(1), Trans. Asme 73, 1951, pp. 31-38.
16. E. Reissner, The effects of transverse Shear Deformation on the bending of elastic-plates, J. Appl. Mech., 12(2), Trans. ASME, vol.67, 1945, pp. 69-77.
17. S. Ahmad, B. Irons, B. M. and O.C. Zienkiewicz - Analysis Of Thick And Thin Shell Structures By Curved Finite Elements. Int. J. Num. Meth. Engng. 2, 1970, pp 419-451
18. R. Bresler and A. C. Scordelis, Shear strength of reinforced concrete beams, ACI Journal, Proceedings, Vol.60, n° 1, 1963, pp. 51-73.